

ISic0607

I.Sicily inscription 0607

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy (not seen on visit to museum 2018-07-16)

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Found in Lipari probably between 1855 and 1864 in contrada Diana

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Cefalù, Museo Mandralisca, inventory 1457

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height 14.5 cm

Width 20 cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Valeria

2. Tryphosa

Apparatus

Text of I.Lipara

Translation**Commentary****Digital identifiers:**

TM 491872

EDR 159493

EDCS 22100611

PHI 334887

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7492 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 779

Libertini, G 1921. Le isole eolie nell'antichità greca e romana. Ricerche storiche ed archeologiche. Florence. At 228 no.5

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0607. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4338079>